

Identifying Dominant Predictors of Student Depression Using Principal Component Analysis

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Abstract

Early identification of depression in university students remains challenging due to multidimensional contributing factors spanning academic, lifestyle, and socioeconomic domains. This study applies Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify compound risk factors that predict depression more effectively than individual variables alone, analyzing a secondary dataset of 27,900 Indian university students across 13 standardized variables including academic pressure, financial stress, sleep duration, and suicidal ideation.

PCA was used to reveal principal components as directions of maximal variance. Component loadings were analyzed to interpret factor composition, and Pearson correlation quantified relationships with depression status. Linear regression modeling assessed predictive strength of the most correlated component.

Results demonstrate that depression emerges from multiple semi-independent pathways rather than a single dominant factor. Notably, the 2nd principal component exhibits exceptional predictive power: loading heavily on academic pressure (0.451), financial stress (0.438), and suicidal thoughts (0.437), it achieves a correlation of $r = -0.707$ ($R^2 = 0.50$) with depression. This compound factor explains approximately 50% of variance in depression status, substantially exceeding any individual predictor (typically $R^2 \approx 0.25-0.30$) and demonstrating that these stressors operate synergistically rather than additively.

These findings suggest PCA-derived compound factors offer superior predictive validity for depression screening in educational settings, though the diffuse variance structure indicates depression's complex, multi-pathway etiology cannot be reduced to fewer than ~9 dimensions without information loss.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale

Mental health, and particularly depression is a prevalent issue, leading to increased suicide rates and issues. Recent CDC data reveals that 40% of U.S. high school students reported persistent feelings of sadness or hopelessness in 2023, representing a concerning 10 percentage point increase from 30% in 2013 (CDC, 2024). In 2024, over 5.2 million American teenagers experienced a major depressive episode, yet more than half received no treatment (Mental Health America, 2024). Work or academic stress is also a prevalent cause of depression and is becoming increasingly common in students. Predicting depression and identifying key causes or correlating sets of factors can be beneficial, to prevent depression in the first place, or identify those who have the highest chance of being depressed.

A variety of factors may contribute to depression, including academic pressure, sleep disruption, financial stress, and socioeconomic factors. Oftentimes, a combination or group of complex, interdependent factors can be linked to depression and isolating or making sense of these multiple dimensions can be challenging.

My personal intersection with the topic of this research paper comes from being around friends and family members who have faced depression. I aspire to use mathematical models to improve people's lives and well being and perhaps the learnings here can be applied to students across schools, to help assess which are possibly facing depression or are in conditions that correlate highly to having depression.

1.2 Aim

This investigation aims to apply principal component analysis (PCA) to a multidimensional student dataset to identify which combinations of demographic, academic, and lifestyle variables form compound factors that correlate most strongly with depression. Specifically, this study seeks to determine whether PCA-derived principal components can predict depression more effectively than individual variables alone, and to quantify the predictive strength of the most correlated component through linear regression modeling.

1.3 Background

Because of the multivariate and interdependent factors involved with depression, evaluating the effect of a single variable in isolation may not capture the full picture. Traditional methods that measure how much a single factor predicts depression can be limited, as they ignore interactions between variables and the complex structure of the data.

Principal component analysis (PCA) offers a more promising approach, as it's a powerful mathematical tool for uncovering structure in high-dimensional data that may reveal certain linked and strongly representative factors. Using PCA, we can reduce the complexity of the data while preserving the essential relationships between features, making it a suitable method for investigating the multidimensional causes of depression.

Many datasets containing data gathered from surveys about depression and these possible linking factors exist. In this study, I used a dataset containing survey information from 27,900 students across many Indian universities (Dhuddi, Z.). The dataset contains gender, age, academic pressure, and many more factors, including whether the student is depressed or not. The dataset was chosen because of its large amount of data samples which is useful for

statistical analysis, and because it was close to ready to use without need for much preprocessing.

To run the statistical analysis across thousands of datapoints and handle the large CSV data files, Python 3.11 was used with the libraries pandas, NumPy, SciPy, Matplotlib.

1.3.1 Mathematical Concepts

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Each vector or 'component' derived from PCA captures the maximal amount of variance in the dataset. The most dominant components "capture" the span which has the most variance in the data set. Figure 1 demonstrates this, showing the first component spanning along the "stretch" of the data points, which is the direction of highest variance. Subsequently, the second most dominant component is the smaller "width" of the data points. Although Figure 1 demonstrates PCA in just 2 dimensions, it can be applied to higher dimensional spaces, to analyze more than just 2 factors. In our dataset, each factor (academic pressure, age, etc.) makes up a dimension in the multidimensional space. A feature of principal components is that they are orthogonal.

Figure 1: Principal component analysis diagram

Z-score Normalization

Because each factor in the data is measured on different scales (Academic pressure: 0-5, Age ~18-30, work/study hours: ~1-8), normalization is required to prevent larger scaled variables from dominating the principal components. A common method used is z-score normalization, where:

$$z_i = \frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma}$$

And z_i is the z-score, x_i is the numerical value, μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the values of that factor, respectively. We can interpret a positive z-score meaning the value is above the mean. And a negative z-score meaning the value is below the mean. Meanwhile, magnitude informs how far the value is from the mean in terms of standard deviations. This method ensures all axes have values at the same scale and that the data is centered around the origin, which is required to find the covariance matrix.

Covariance Matrix

Covariance is a statistical measure that indicates how much two variables change together. For PCA, the covariance matrix C captures joint variability between variables each and every variable. The covariance matrix is first constructed from a set of data X with n observations and p where each column is a factor or variable, and each row is a datapoint.

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1p} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{np} \end{bmatrix}$$

If and only if each value in the column is centered around that column's mean $X_{i,j} - \mu_j$, then the covariance matrix in matrix form is:

$$C = \frac{1}{n} X^T X$$

More depth on covariance is given in Section 2.

Principal Components

The principal components are the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix with the greatest eigenvalues. These represent directions along which the most variance, or 'information' is captured.

Projection onto a Vector

For a data point x and unit vector v , the scalar projection is $x^T v$, which measures how far x extends in direction v . When applied to all rows in the set of data X , the vector Xv contains all n projected values. The variance of the projections, $Var(Xv)$, quantifies how much information is captured in direction v .

Proportion of Variance

The Proportion of Variance Explained (PVE) shows how much of the total variance is captured by a specific principal component or a set of components as a value in $[0, 1]$. It's a measure of how "representative" each reduced dimension is. This is useful to explore the extent to which principal component analysis (PCA) can identify latent factors within a multidimensional student dataset. For example, if the top 10 principal components only explain 50% of the variance in the dataset, that shows that half of the information in the dataset is not captured by these components, meaning PCA is not very effective at finding latent factors in depression data.

Pearson's Correlation

Pearson product moment correlation is a statistical measure of the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two continuous variables. A value close to $+ 1$ or $- 1$ indicates a strong linear relationship. A value close to 0 indicates a weak or non-existent linear relationship.

In this to the study, it can find the correlation between the magnitude of certain latent, compounded factors (those derived from PCA) and depression. We can evaluate whether these are better predictors and correlate higher with depression than any individual metric.

1.4 Assumptions

The mathematical tools used in this study carry several limitations.

Firstly, some factors that contribute to depression may be nonlinear or more nuanced in ways that PCA cannot detect. For example, if the correlation between academic pressure and depression is non-linear (both too-low and too-high academic pressure correlates with depression), PCA would fail to meaningfully extract that pattern.

Additionally, the depression metric in the dataset is a discrete, binary classification between “depressed” and “not depressed”. This limits the applicability and effectiveness of certain our PCA, which works best with continuous variables. Pearson's correlation coefficient also expects to work with continuous values. That said, Pearson’s correlation can still be representative as long as one variable is continuous.

Similarly, categorical variables like gender, profession, or city are excluded or simplified, which could ignore important information and factors contributing to depression.

Lastly, the dataset may not be representative of all students, as it comes from specific universities in India, and we are unsure of the methodological rigor that went into collecting the information. This may hinder the applicability of findings in this paper. However this should not affect the process or results of the mathematical processing itself.

2. Mathematical Processing and Interpretation

2.1 Data Preparation

The data set comes with 27,900 data points, each with values across the following 16 factors. Data preprocessing was a requirement in order to make the data most compatible and functional for principal component analysis. Below is a sample of the first 4 data points from the unprocessed data.

Variable	Entry 1	Entry 2	Entry 3	Entry 4
id	2	8	26	30
Gender	Male	Female	Male	Female
Age	33.0	24.0	31.0	28.0
City	Visakhapatnam	Bangalore	Srinagar	Varanasi

Profession	Student	Student	Student	Student
Academic Pressure	5.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
Work Pressure	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
CGPA	8.97	5.9	7.03	5.59
Study Satisfaction	2.0	5.0	5.0	2.0
Job Satisfaction	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Sleep Duration	5–6 hours	5–6 hours	Less than 5 hours	7–8 hours
Dietary Habits	Healthy	Moderate	Healthy	Moderate
Degree	B.Pharm	BSc	BA	BCA
Suicidal Thoughts	Yes	No	No	Yes
Work/Study Hours	3.0	3.0	9.0	4.0
Financial Stress	1.0	2.0	1.0	5.0
Family History of Mental Illness	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Depression	1	0	0	1

Table 1: Sample of first 4 data points in the unprocessed student depression dataset. Note: in this table, columns are entries, however this choice was done to fit the data within the page. The matrix representation of the dataset has each entry as a row.

As not every variable is interpretable as a continuous or even numerical value which is required for PCA, the preprocessing includes removing certain variables or converting them into numerical values. The following are the variables are kept from the unprocessed dataset:

- Age (18–59)

- Academic Pressure (0–5 scale)
- Work Pressure (0–5 scale)
- CGPA (0–10)
- Study Satisfaction (0–5 scale)
- Job Satisfaction (0–4 scale)
- Work/Study Hours (0–12)
- Financial Stress (1–5 scale)

Next, are categorical variables that were included but converted into a numerical value:

- Sleep Duration: convert ranges to mid-point hours (e.g., “5–6 hours” → 5.5)
- Suicidal Thoughts: Yes = 1, No = 0
- Family History of Mental Illness: Yes = 1, No = 0
- Gender: changed to Is Female? Yes = 1, No (Male) = 0
- Dietary Habits: numeric encoding (Unhealthy = 0, Moderate = 1, Healthy = 2)

All other factors were excluded:

- id
- Profession
- Degree
- City

Lastly, because depression is the dependent variable, we excluded it. Next, to construct the covariance matrix, the data values had to be normalized (which also includes centering data around the mean). Firstly, the means μ and standard deviations σ were calculated for each variable. Each individual data point x_i was then recorded as a z-score normalized value z_i :

$$z_i = \frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma}$$

Note: z-score normalized values are rounded for space

2.2 Deriving the Mathematics of PCA

2.2.1 Constructing the Covariance Matrix

The covariance matrix stores the covariances of every two variables and is symmetrical. The general formula for covariance is:

$$\text{Cov}(X, Y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})$$

Where \bar{X} , \bar{Y} are the means of any two random variables X and Y .

We can rewrite the matrix X , where x_i^\top is a row vector, representing each data point containing $d = 13$ values (each being the normalized values for age, academic pressure, etc.):

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_1^\top \\ x_2^\top \\ \vdots \\ x_n^\top \end{bmatrix}, \quad x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d.$$

Then to calculate the covariance C_{jk} for any two variables j and k across the data set (with $n = 27900$ entries):

$$C_{jk} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} x_{ik}.$$

This calculation is the basis for each entry in the covariance matrix. Note that the z-normalized values already center the values, which is required for calculating covariance, therefore the two values x_{ij} and x_{ik} can be multiplied directly. The summation can actually be written as a simpler matrix multiplication which does the exact same thing:

$$C = \frac{1}{n} X^T X$$

Doing this calculation on our dataset X , we get the following covariance matrix:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0000 & -0.0763 & 0.0020 & 0.0049 & 0.0093 & -0.0004 & -0.0331 & -0.0949 & -0.0037 & -0.1135 & -0.0049 & -0.0091 & 0.0577 \\ -0.0763 & 1.0003 & -0.0223 & -0.0223 & -0.1112 & -0.0250 & 0.0959 & 0.1520 & -0.0424 & 0.2616 & 0.0298 & 0.0222 & -0.0895 \\ 0.0020 & -0.0223 & 1.0012 & -0.0510 & -0.0212 & 0.7716 & -0.0055 & 0.0019 & 0.0017 & -0.0010 & -0.0062 & -0.0087 & 0.0063 \\ 0.0049 & -0.0223 & -0.0510 & 1.0000 & -0.0437 & -0.0537 & 0.0029 & 0.0058 & -0.0049 & 0.0082 & -0.0043 & -0.0357 & -0.0017 \\ 0.0093 & -0.1112 & -0.0212 & -0.0437 & 0.9998 & -0.0219 & -0.0367 & -0.0652 & 0.0122 & -0.0833 & -0.0035 & 0.0157 & 0.0202 \\ -0.0004 & -0.0250 & 0.7716 & -0.0537 & -0.0219 & 1.0012 & -0.0052 & 0.0053 & -0.0002 & -0.0034 & -0.0100 & -0.0072 & 0.0018 \\ -0.0331 & 0.0959 & -0.0055 & 0.0029 & -0.0367 & -0.0052 & 0.9998 & 0.0752 & -0.0276 & 0.1218 & 0.0175 & -0.0131 & -0.0297 \\ -0.0949 & 0.1520 & 0.0019 & 0.0058 & -0.0652 & 0.0053 & 0.0752 & 0.9999 & -0.0037 & 0.2092 & 0.0086 & 0.0055 & -0.0873 \\ -0.0037 & -0.0424 & 0.0017 & -0.0049 & 0.0122 & -0.0002 & -0.0276 & -0.0037 & 1.0001 & -0.0519 & -0.0122 & 0.0007 & -0.0027 \\ -0.1135 & 0.2616 & -0.0010 & 0.0082 & -0.0833 & -0.0034 & 0.1218 & 0.2092 & -0.0519 & 1.0000 & 0.0261 & 0.0013 & -0.1128 \\ -0.0049 & 0.0298 & -0.0062 & -0.0043 & -0.0035 & -0.0100 & 0.0175 & 0.0086 & -0.0122 & 0.0261 & 1.0000 & 0.0158 & -0.0050 \\ -0.0091 & 0.0222 & -0.0087 & -0.0357 & 0.0157 & -0.0072 & -0.0131 & 0.0055 & 0.0007 & 0.0013 & 0.0158 & 1.0000 & 0.0597 \\ 0.0577 & -0.0895 & 0.0063 & -0.0017 & 0.0202 & 0.0018 & -0.0297 & -0.0873 & -0.0027 & -0.1128 & -0.0050 & 0.0597 & 1.0000 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note: entries are rounded for space

Notice how the matrix is symmetrical because $Cov(X, Y) = Cov(Y, X)$. Additionally, the diagonals of the matrix contain just the variance of a single variable due to the identity $Cov(X, X) = Var(X)$; they are all 1.000 because the data set was normalized prior. I also found this heatmap to help me visualize the variables which also variate together strongly:

Figure 2: Covariance matrix as a heatmap

We can see for example, in row 6, column 3, the covariance between job satisfaction and work pressure is moderately high at ~ 0.772 . Mathematically, $Cov(X_3, X_6) \approx 0.772$.

Interpreting this means that increased work pressure correlates with higher job satisfaction. This initially struck me as counterintuitive as I had expected work pressure to correlate with lower job satisfaction. However, reflecting on this finding, I hypothesized two possible explanations: (1) students with internships/jobs that challenge them may feel more engaged and satisfied, or (2) this represents students who have jobs (both pressure and satisfaction >0) versus those who don't (both ≈ 0). To test this, I filtered the dataset to only students with non-zero work pressure and the data revealed that only 3 out of 27,900 students (0.01%)

had non-zero work pressure. This meant the high covariance was only reflecting the binary split between students with jobs versus those without, rather than being a meaningful relationship.

2.2.2 Computing Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors

To find the principal components, we consider a vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^{13}$ that captures the direction of maximal variance in the dataset. For any unit vector v , the variance of the projected data, Xv onto v , Xv is:

$$\text{Var}(Xv) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^T v)^2$$

$$(x_i^T v)^2 = (x_i^T v)(x_i^T v) = (x_i^T v)(v^T x_i) = x_i^T (vv^T) x_i$$

$$\text{Var}(Xv) = \frac{1}{n} (Xv)^T (Xv) = \frac{1}{n} v^T X^T X v = v^T \left[\frac{1}{n} X^T X \right] v = v^T C v$$

The first principal component is obtained by solving the optimisation problem to find the v that maximizes variance:

$$\max_{\|v\|=1} v^T C v$$

Notice how this is just maximizing the dot product of v and Cv :

$$v^T C v = \text{dot}(v, Cv).$$

To maximize a dot product of two vectors, they must lie on the same span. Cv can only lie on the same span as v if v is an eigenvector of C . Finding the optimal v becomes a problem of finding C 's eigenvectors. While the corresponding eigenvalues dictate the relative amount of variance each eigenvector captures. In general, the n th principal component is the eigenvector of C with the n th largest eigenvalue.

We used technology to solve for all of C 's eigenvectors PC and eigenvalues λ . These are just the top 3 for demonstration:

$$\lambda_1 = 1.7832, \quad PC_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0211 \\ 0.0692 \\ -0.7003 \\ 0.0911 \\ 0.0139 \\ -0.7005 \\ 0.0302 \\ 0.0279 \\ -0.0098 \\ 0.0469 \\ 0.0198 \\ 0.0107 \\ -0.0269 \end{bmatrix} \quad \lambda_2 = 1.6293, \quad PC_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2624 \\ -0.4843 \\ -0.0643 \\ -0.0004 \\ 0.2364 \\ -0.0649 \\ -0.2741 \\ -0.4309 \\ 0.0943 \\ -0.5346 \\ -0.0640 \\ 0.0115 \\ 0.2695 \end{bmatrix} \quad \lambda_3 = 1.0709, \quad PC_3 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.1070 \\ 0.1260 \\ -0.0182 \\ -0.5303 \\ 0.2544 \\ -0.0181 \\ 0.0145 \\ 0.0171 \\ -0.0794 \\ 0.0481 \\ 0.2527 \\ 0.6831 \\ 0.2939 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3: Heatmap of principal components and how much of each variable they are made up of

By considering just the top few principal components, it makes it possible to reduce the number of components in consideration down to just the top few that capture the largest variance and information in the depression data. We can see from the heatmap above that many of the first few principal components show groups of factors that tend to come together. PC_2 suggests academic pressure, financial stress, suicidal thoughts, and lower age tend to be related and come together.

2.3 Variance Analysis

The proportion of variance explained (PVE) shows how much of the total variance is captured by a specific principal component or a set of components as a value in $[0, 1]$. It's a measure of how "representative" each reduced dimension is. PVE for the i -th principal component is calculated as:

$$PVE_i = \frac{\lambda_i}{\sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_j}$$

Where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_p$ are all the eigenvalues of the covariance matrix and λ_i is the eigenvalue corresponding to the i -th principal component. We can use it to quantify how much information the top- k principal components can represent:

$$Cumulative\ PVE = \sum_{i=1}^k PVE_i$$

This is useful to explore the extent to which principal component analysis (PCA) can identify latent factors within a multidimensional student dataset. The PVE for all 14 principal components were plotted, along with a scree plot:

Figure 4 (left): Variance explained by each principal component. Figure 5 (right): Cumulative variance explained by principal components.

Figure 6: Scree plot shows eigenvalues of the principal components. Shows the same information as Figure 4.

In Figure 4, the equal variance threshold (red dashed line at 7.7%) represents $1/13 \approx 7.7\%$, which is the variance each component would explain if all variables were uncorrelated. Components exceeding this threshold ($PC_1 - PC_4$) capture more information than a single original variable, suggesting they represent meaningful compound factors. However only two

principal components are meaningfully above the Kaiser criterion, which is a heuristic stating that we should only consider factors with an eigenvalue greater than one. An eigenvalue greater than one signifies that the factor explains more variance than a single original variable, making it a significant component to keep.

Figure 5 shows that all of the principal components, seldom the first 4, aren't any better at capturing variance than the single factors alone, being below the Kaiser criterion. Also the cumulative variance chart is nearly linear, showing that PCA doesn't provide a significantly compressed representation of factors. I initially imagined that the graph would instead show a the steeper initial gradient with early plateau as that would signify high variance capture in the initial principle components. The first 9 principal components (out of 13) only reaches 80% of variance being captured. 90% variance captured was only achieved with 12 principal components, meaning that PCA doesn't do an effective job at reducing the dimensionality and identifying a latent structure for our data set while retaining information.

PCA struggles to compress the data into just a few top vectors aligns with psychological research showing depression has multiple contributing pathways (academic stress, financial pressure, sleep disruption, family history) that operate semi-independently and non-linearly rather than collapsing into a single "distress" dimension.

2.4 Linking PCA to Depression

2.4.1 Correlation Analysis

We can evaluate whether the principal components are better predictors and correlate higher with depression than any individual metric through Pearson's product moment correlation:

$$r_{XY} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}}$$

r represents the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two continuous variables. The correlation coefficient between depression and principal components (left) and individual variables (right) were plotted:

Figure 7 (left) and 8 (right): Shows the sorted correlation between principal analysis, variables and depression.

PC_2 shows a strong, positive correlation with depression, this likely represents a combination of stress, sleep, and other factors that together correlate more strongly with depression than any individual variable. This is an example of where PCA dimensionality reduction has revealed a more informative underlying pattern, which can be useful for predicting, diagnosing and identifying sets or combinations of causes for depression. Looking back at Figure 3, we see a combination of suicidal thoughts, academic pressure and financial stress contributing towards a high correlation with depression. This makes perfect sense, as those

same 3 variables are the top variables with correlation to depression (left of Figure 7) and PCA finds that these stressors compound synergistically.

Although the correlation is strong, this doesn't guarantee causation; just that this combination of factors moves with depression scores. Additionally, the top principle component does not inherently make it likely to be associated with depression. PCA simply groups commonly associated values into one direction that maximally captures variation; it can be used to simplify the handling or consideration of tens of factors into 1.

2.4.2 Evaluating Predictive Strength

The exceptionally high correlation of PC_2 makes it a strong candidate predictor of depression. To explore this paper's goal quantitatively, we fit a linear regression model between PC_2 and depression status and then statistically verify its accuracy.

To understand how much variance PC_2 explains in depression, we calculate the coefficient of determination:

$$r^2 = (-0.707)^2 = 0.50$$

PC_2 accounts for approximately 50% of the variance in depression status. This is remarkably high for a single predictor variable, especially one derived without directly using depression information during PCA construction.

For context, in psychological and social science research, an r^2 of 0.50 is considered a very strong effect. Individual variables like academic pressure typically explain only 20-30% of variance ($r^2 \approx 0.25-0.30$), making PC_2 's performance substantially superior.

The remaining 50% of unexplained variance suggests depression has additional complexity potentially caused by unmeasured factors, non-linear interactions with other factors or nonlinear effects (e.g., very low and very high academic pressure both correlating with depression)

2.4.3 Significance Test

Using a t-test for correlation significance with sample size $n = 27900$:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

$$t = -0.707 \times \sqrt{\frac{27898}{1-0.50}} = -166.9765$$

With a t-value of -166.9765 , $p \approx 0$ due to the massive sample size providing extremely high statistical confidence, confirming the correlation is not due to chance.

2.4.4 Creating a Model

Creating a linear model to estimate the probability of a student being depressed:

$$P(\text{Depressed}) = a \times PC_{2, \text{score}} + c$$

To get a $PC_{2, \text{score}}$ from a single entry of processed data $V \in \mathbb{R}^{n=13}$, projecting the set of student data is onto PC_2 required:

$$PC_{2, \text{score}} = PC_2 \cdot V$$

This dot product gives how strongly a student's data 'aligns' with the principal component.

Next we use a linear regression to find values of a and c :

$$a = -0.273, c = 0.585, R^2 = 0.4993$$

Figure 9: Linear regression of $PC_{2, \text{score}}$ and depression

It is important to consider that the linear regression does not perform best with the binary classification of depression, rather, having a continuous range of values is preferred. Values in between 1 and 0 our model can be interpreted as a probability landscape, without certain classification.

Figure 10: The overlap region represents students whose risk factors (as captured by PC2) are ambiguous. They may have moderate levels of academic pressure, financial stress, and suicidal ideation that don't clearly place them in either group. This aligns with clinical understanding that depression exists on a spectrum rather than as a binary state.

3. Conclusion

This investigation aimed to explore the extent to which principal component analysis (PCA) can identify latent factors within a multidimensional student dataset and determine how strongly these factors correlate with depression levels. By reducing the dataset to a few principal components, this study sought to uncover which combinations of demographic, academic, and lifestyle variables capture the majority of variation in student characteristics and to evaluate how effectively these reduced dimensions explain differences in reported depression.

3.1 Extent of Success

PCA partially succeeded in revealing meaningful structure within the depression dataset, though with notable limitations. The analysis revealed that no single dominant factor drives depression; rather, it emerges from multiple semi-independent pathways. PC1 explained 18.4% of variance and PC2 explained 11.8%, indicating that depression is influenced by many diffuse variables rather than collapsing into one or two clear underlying dimensions. However, PC2's exceptionally strong correlation with depression ($r = -0.707$, $R^2 = 0.50$) demonstrates that PCA successfully identified a compound factor—combining academic pressure, financial stress, and suicidal thoughts—that predicts depression substantially better than any individual variable alone.

The need for 9 components to capture 80% of cumulative variance suggests PCA cannot compress depression factors into just 2-3 dominant dimensions, which aligns with psychological research showing depression has multiple contributing pathways operating semi-independently. Despite this complexity, the regression model using PC2 as a single predictor achieved $R^2 = 0.4993$, meaning it explains approximately 50% of variance in depression status—a remarkably strong result for psychological research where individual predictors typically explain only 20-30%.

3.2 Limitations

Several limitations constrain the scope and applicability of our findings.

Firstly, the dataset originates from specific universities in India, potentially limiting generalizability to other cultural contexts, educational systems, or geographic regions. The methodological rigor of the original survey collection is unclear, which may affect data reliability.

The most significant limitation stems from treating depression as a binary variable (depressed vs. not depressed) rather than a continuous severity scale. This reduces the effectiveness of both PCA and Pearson correlation, which perform optimally with continuous data. Despite this, correlation coefficients remain interpretable as effect sizes, and the strong results suggest the relationship would be even clearer with granular depression measurements.

Another limitation is that because PCA assumes linear relationships between variables it fails to capture nonlinear patterns. For instance, if both very low and very high academic pressure correlate with depression (a U-shaped relationship), PCA would miss this interaction entirely. The 50% unexplained variance in depression suggests such nonlinear effects or unmeasured factors may be at play.

Lastly, converting categorical variables (gender, dietary habits, sleep duration) into numerical scales introduces artificial ordinality and may not fully represent their true relationships with depression. Additionally, excluding variables like city, profession, and degree removes potentially meaningful contextual information. Methods such as one-hot encoding could be explored to address this.

3.3 Improvements

The most critical improvement would be collecting depression data on a continuous severity scale (e.g., PHQ-9 scores ranging 0-27) rather than binary classification. This would unlock the full power of PCA and correlation analysis while better reflecting the spectrum nature of depression.

Another improvement could be to use advanced regression techniques like replacing linear regression with logistic regression would better handle the binary outcome if severity data remains unavailable. Alternatively, nonlinear models such as polynomial regression or decision trees could capture complex interactions between variables that linear methods

miss. Additionally, applying techniques like t-SNE or UMAP over PCA could reveal manifold structures in the data that PCA's linear assumptions overlook.

Lastly, more ranging psychological measurements and factors could have made the findings more widely applicable. Collecting detailed data on specific stressors, coping strategies, social support networks, and life events would provide richer information for PCA to identify meaningful latent factors.

References

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2024). Youth Risk Behavior Survey Data Summary & Trends Report: 2013-2023. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/healthyyouth/data/yrbs/index.htm>

Mental Health America. (2024). The State of Mental Health in America 2024. Retrieved from <https://mhanational.org/issues/state-mental-health-america>

Dhuddi, Z. (2024). Student Mental Health & Depression Indicators Dataset. Kaggle. Retrieved from <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/zubairdhuddi/student-dataset>

All graphs, images, diagrams and formulas were self-made and designed.